

ISS Denmark

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What characterizes our business?

Our purpose: Connecting people and places to make the world work better.

ISS is "a leading workplace experience and facility management company, providing comprehensive, high-quality solutions through engaged employees who contribute to better business results and make life easier, more productive, and pleasant for everyone" (ISS World.com).

Globally, ISS has approximately 360,000+ employees, about 40,000+ clients, and operates in 30+ countries. In Denmark, there are about 6,500 employees and about 500-600 (primarily middle) managers.

The company delivers services at approximately 1,000 locations.

The company has four main sectors: food, cleaning, technical services, and workplace experience.

It is a "low margin industry", where 70-80% of the total costs are tied to human resources. "Our product is essentially motivated employees". Therefore, it is necessary to treat employees properly, and ISS's success is built on putting a lot of effort into recruiting the right people, education, career development, the opportunity to advance, etc. The turnover of staff is therefore moderate under the circumstances. It would have been higher if employees were not treated properly.

The type of business (low margin industry) necessitates a short-term economic focus and requires discipline and decisiveness. This is the context in which investments are made. The company is good at extinguishing fires, pivoting, and solving problems urgently, e.g., if a customer suddenly has a new need for a specific service.

The company is cost-conscious, lean, operationally oriented, and pragmatic, so problems are solved literally "with elbow grease and hard work". As one interviewee expressed:

"We live with uncertainty as a condition of existence. We are accustomed to adjusting up and down, adding or removing a new business segment, and devising new strategies. We aim to be "best in class", but it must not come at the expense of behaving properly, internally and externally. We are characterized by an opportunity-driven mindset, seeing the glass as half-full, not half-empty. We are attitudinally aligned with the labor organization (employer/employee), so the employees and their organizations agree with us. We have a strong People &

Culture concept, and it supports the HR business. When COVID-19 struck, we had a common enemy; we came closer together, and people understood the decisions that were made".

The company is a "two-headed monster" trying to combine the best of two worlds:

- There is an extreme production focus, where work *just needs* to be done, cost what it may ("the mail must go out"), and it brings a short-term focus, always bearing in mind that this is a low margin business. But at the same time, it is a company with its heart in the right place and room for care, solidarity, and humanity
- The strict focus on systems, procedures, and rules coexists with autonomy, local self-determination, but this can involve difficult dilemmas and decisions.

A paradigm shift is occurring these years from many smaller customers (companies) that "had cleaning done Monday and Tuesday" to more and more very large customers (including international companies, e.g., some of the world's largest banks), which have broad and varied service packages. This places enormous demands on the company to consider things like compliance, ESG, GDPR, data security/discipline in the product – and to equip employees and managers to handle and act in this complex context. It also poses significant management demands to lead employees who "must share their heart between the employer (ISS) and the client where they spend their total working hours," so they say, "I work for ISS at Company XX".

It is a challenge that the company is constantly exposed to (and must be able to handle) changing demands and opportunities from outside and within, where, among other things, customers come and go, and the company has a high turnover of personnel, and where the desire for corporate alignment and uniformity (One ISS) must be combined with decentralized decision-making, operational flexibility and adaptation to customers' characteristics and needs/wants. It is a concrete dilemma how to implement "the big ISS" while tailoring client delivery to each individual client. The aim is to stay within the overarching frameworks – or at least not deviate too far from them.

Collectively, the company aims to attract more and more large, complex customers who need integrated services and on-site, present management. "Integrated facility service" is the term for the 360-degree service where ISS handles most functions not tied to the core business. This can include cafeteria services, cleaning, interior maintenance, reception, security, assistance with recruitment and onboarding, IT tasks, etc.

A large part of the workforce is unskilled, and many have an ethnic background other than Danish. In the public eye (and indirectly therefore also in the employees' self-image), cleaning and kitchen jobs have low status, and salary is the primary motivational factor. If higher wages can be obtained at other companies, it does not take much to seek elsewhere, and it may even be for other job types, e.g., retail and warehouse. Generally, the wage level for unskilled workers at ISS is, however, on the higher side compared to what can be obtained within other realistic job categories – and especially higher than what the wages are at some of ISS' competitors.

OneISS Strategy

The overarching strategy is as follows:

OneISS

With the OneISS strategy, we aim to strengthen our reputation as the most respected global leader in integrated facility services and as a leader in the cleaning field. We will achieve this by enhancing, simplifying, and working more closely within ISS. With the OneISS strategy, which is based on the company's global strengths, we are focused on executing activities and delivering results.

The strategy includes three goals:

Making ISS stronger, simpler, closer

Stronger

We aim to become the most respected global leader in integrated facility services and enhance our position as a leader in the cleaning field by investing in expertise, quality, efficiency, and technology to deliver better services and products tailored to the needs of our customers.

Simpler

We will improve our key account strategy – for the benefit of all our stakeholders – by delivering better outcomes to customers, with a more commercial focus and a new service-driven approach, thereby improving quality, efficiency, and the company's compliance.

Closer

We will bring our country teams closer to customers while acting as one global team – we reward appropriate behavior and leadership by linking our incentives to the strategy's implementation.

The purpose of this strategy is to unify the company, create uniformity, and implement corporate-wide systems (e.g., IT infrastructure). This is coupled with a desire for streamlining, standardization, and systems – and thereby leveraging the size that ISS has, especially globally.

We want to move more decision-making power into the corporate management, create cohesion – not just cooperation. In implementing this, it is essential that it impacts HR practices, e.g., people reviews.

In relation to customers, the motto is: "Service with a human touch".

The efforts to create "OneISS" are perceived within the organization as both positive and negative. It is positive because, in the organization (especially among middle managers), they know what "Big ISS" wants and demands, because they can follow in its wake, because they therefore do not need to "reinvent the wheel," and because they have arguments to tell employees: "This is how it is!". However, it also has a negative side, because at the individual location there may be a need for situation-adapted, pragmatic approaches, which may not quite harmonize with what is communicated from central management.

A Culture Created Over Decades

ISS is permeated with decisiveness, decentralized decision-making ability, and extensive autonomy for country managers, service managers, and individual employees. Emphasis is placed on teamwork, there is respect for the individual, and if a mistake is made, it is not one person but the team that has made the mistake.

People are accustomed to raising their hand when they have a problem, they reach out to others, and those reached out to typically want to support and help, so problems are solved quickly and easily. Respect for the individual is both a cause and a consequence of the culture. Because it is a "people business", human resources are both a shortcut to and a prerequisite for performance and earnings. As a company, therefore, there is no choice but to focus on the employee.

It requires managers who can create engagement. If not, the potential is not released, and this results in both poor earnings and low morale. This realization is not new. It is rooted in the organization and a result of many decades of focus on human resources.

The Current Cultural Picture

The values are very prominent in the current situation. Admittedly, there may be a certain amount of rhetoric or hot air in these values, but they are experienced, felt, and lived out in everyday life:

The five values are:

Unity

We trust each other and believe in creating equality, inclusion, and cohesion for everyone – a culture where everyone can be themselves. We trust.

Honesty

We do not compromise our honesty. We respect our customers, our colleagues, and our company. We show respect.

Responsibility

Indifference is immoral. We engage in our work and those we work for. We show care.

Entrepreneurship

Action means more than words. All our employees have the right to act, and we expect them to do so. We act.

Quality

We are passionate about delivering high quality. We keep our promises. We deliver the goods.

(See elaboration in the appendix).

The strong loyalty experienced among employees is due, in part, to the experience *that* the company has a long history, *that* it is shaped by Danish culture, *that* one is part of something larger by working for ISS, *that* there is relatively little distance between high and low, *that* one can work one's way up from the floor, *that* there are good educational opportunities, *that* the quality of managers is generally high, and *that* there are rarely labor conflicts. There is generally a culture of recognition, where knowledge and experiences are shared with others, rather than being kept to oneself in an attempt to shine, (which typically leads to unconstructive competition and suboptimization).

Middle Managers – A Crucial Actor

"The floor managers have been the everyday heroes – and have carried ISS through the COVID-19 crisis".

A very important pivot in the company is the so-called service managers, who are the company's bridgehead, ambassador, and link to customers. At large customers, an "independent business unit" is even created, so ISS employees and service managers are physically located at the customer. Large customers can thus have many hundreds of ISS employees and their managers residing with them, almost as an embedded unit. This was of great significance for the implementation of company-conceived plans, guidelines for handling COVID-19 could be pushed all the way to the outermost link.

Overall, ISS has very good middle managers. The job is inherently developmental, but the company tops up with a good selection as well as talent and leadership development programs. This is important for retention, and there are many examples of rapid career paths from unskilled (e.g., café or cleaning worker) to middle management level. This is partly possible because, as mentioned, ISS is a distinctly operational organization with a pragmatic mindset, short decision processes, and great adaptability when urgent interventions are needed.

Diversity calls for present and individually tailored leadership. Since recruitment is very broad, including marginal groups, people on the fringes of the labor market, people hired under special conditions, etc., service managers often need to go far in terms of personal assistance or outright care, e.g., by assisting employees with contacting the municipality, filling out forms, etc.

Middle managers are the most exposed. They stand in the eye of the storm, they must be able to do everything, they must have an unconditional customer focus ("Everything we do should be for the customer"), they must manage and lead a staff with great diversity, etc. It is a question of whether the company supports middle managers sufficiently HR-wise and gives them sufficiently attractive conditions, e.g., salary.

During COVID-19, middle managers played an incredibly large role, as described below. They were a driving force throughout the process, they were able to set and clarify direction, they could demonstrate presence for employees, and they radiated a basic attitude: "We will also solve this crisis....". They even often had to "step over the threshold" and help employees with personal matters, e.g., filling out forms and dealing with the municipality.

HR Work Organization

Because the company is a "people business", HR plays a central role, is respected, is recognized as a competitive parameter, and has a place at the table. HR is business-driven, based on a strong business partner model, and these business partners play a significant role because they are close to operations and operate from a business perspective.

At ISS, it has never been a question of whether HR should sit at the table where decisions are made. The pandemic has not changed this, but the role that HR played in COVID-19 was a new and different one. The complexity and importance of the issues HR dealt with manifested HR's significance to the organization. The influence was already significant, but it became even greater. This is illustrated below.

As a result of the company's, products', and surrounding society's character, recruitment plays a crucial role. There is a massive focus on diversity and inclusivity in the workforce. This includes, for example, minority groups, people with disabilities, people on the fringes of the labor market, refugees, etc.

Great emphasis is placed on leadership education, the development of a talent pool, so talents are prepared to take on the demanding middle management jobs and possibly be equipped for further promotions. However, the company is weaker on the systems side.

Therefore, there is a focus on increased use of shared service units, automation, use of AI, chatbots, etc.

Interaction with Trade Unions and Employee Representatives

As has been somewhat categorically and squarely expressed: "ISS would not exist today if we did not have the Danish model" and thus the tradition of close cooperation between the employer and employee sides, backed up by the state. This was also unconditionally crucial – and to great benefit – during COVID-19, partly because it rests on the Danish welfare state and the economic tools that were deployed. During COVID-19, this manifested itself in tripartite negotiations (labor market parties and the government), the possibility of wage compensation, work sharing, etc. In this light, the company was able to operate the business and, among other things, create partnership cooperation with customers. From a helicopter perspective, it can be said that none of the major players in the Danish model got everything they wanted, but everyone got something – and became a little happier.

For several large personnel groups at ISS (especially cleaning), there is an overall formalized context: Collective agreements, a cooperation secretariat, staff representatives, occupational health and safety representatives, and an institutional context of employer and employee organizations (especially DI and 3F), which employers and employees can lean on. In addition, there is a company committee (= a merger of the main cooperation committee and the main safety committee). The largest agreement is the service agreement that covers cleaning.

However, there is not an extensive network of decentralized employee representatives, which is partly due to the relatively low unionization rate in the sector. (The exact figure is uncertain, but it is around 20-30%). The entire sector is a "grey zone", and many employees come from other countries where union organization is modest.

The role of the cooperation secretary, which is quite unique in relation to the company and the sector as a whole, includes the following tasks:

- Link between the employees (only members) and the trade union 3F
- Entering into local agreements, especially when there is no local staff representative
- Helpdesk regarding inquiries from employees and managers
- Participation in §5 meetings (= takeover of existing employees when entering into – and changing – existing customer contracts)
- Participation in job fairs, e.g., when it came to recruiting Ukrainian refugees.

When COVID-19 occurred, cooperation intensified – also at the industry level – because everyone faced the same challenges and societal demands. But there was not a large network of decentralized employee representatives involved in and shaping how COVID-19 was handled.

In a way, it is an advantage that one is woven into legislation, collective agreements, and occupational health regulations, as it makes it easier to sit down with the employer/employee organizations and negotiate a – for all – good solution. "Collective agreements are there to protect employees", as it was expressed, but this necessitates that these agreements keep up with the times, reflect current labor market conditions, and do not drag their feet in relation to old battle arenas.

Employees and their organizations rarely come with unreasonable demands because it's clear that there's a common, overarching interest in the future of the company. ISS, being a very large company, is also bound and limited by the general agreements made in the field. This means, for example, that you cannot "just" decide to raise the wage level to mitigate the very large and consequential problems currently present with respect to recruitment and retention of employees.

The COVID-19 crisis both pressured and created openings in the contractual area. Occupational boundaries are protected, so certain groups of employees with specific tasks receive a corresponding wage. However, COVID-19 created major shifts in labor needs and supply within various areas. As remote work became more prevalent among clients (companies), for instance, there was less need for cafeteria staff. Conversely, there was a significant increase in certain types of cleaning, spurred by COVID-19 itself. Informally, on an ad hoc basis and on a small scale, employees were therefore transferred across traditional occupational boundaries. However, care was taken to ensure that this was not used as a method to transfer employees to a collective bargaining area with lower wages.

How occupational boundaries and flexibility are experienced also depends on the workplace the client has. In connection with new contracts, there is often a business transfer of the client's existing employees. Especially with public clients, ISS experiences that transferred employees adhere to previous frameworks and procedures and may find it difficult to understand and accept the flexibility, dynamism, and entrepreneurial spirit that characterize ISS.

In short: There is some hesitation about horizontal job changes, and a condition is that "the employee gets a little something for it", as it is expressed.

ISS emphasizes having – and adhering to – fixed frameworks and rules, complying with agreements, and not cutting corners regarding socially responsible management (e.g.,

sustainability, environment, climate, diversity, etc.). This is deeply rooted in the company's culture, and there is increasing pressure from corporate and public clients that one "must behave properly", and these clients increasingly have their own social clauses that must be adhered to by suppliers. It is far too risky if the reputation of clients and/or ISS is tarnished by scandals and public outrage on social media.

As it was expressed:

"We are a decent player in an unorganized market, where there are many shady competitors or companies of the type "Mr. and Mrs. Bucket around the corner". We have no choice with the clients we have. We do not win on price. Decency and societal pressure (including sustainability, diversity, environment, AI, etc.) are increasingly important – also in clients' own value propositions and their demands on us. And we cannot attract good people if we do not behave properly".

ISS is very aware of – and must relate to and act based on – the fact that the industry includes a dark land of both competitors and labor organizations, which, in ISS' eyes, have another (read: problematic) negotiation practice.

Generally, ISS struggles with some reputation challenges. The company is primarily/exclusively perceived as a cleaning company and thus belongs to a sector with a bad image, low status and, in the public's eyes, is staffed by employees with an ethnic background other than Danish, who receive low pay and have poor working conditions. Thus, the broad scope of integrated facility services, which is the company's hallmark, is overlooked – and so too is the company's prioritization of labor market agreements (e.g., collective agreements), good working conditions, good management, social responsibility, diversity, and high ethical standards.

The National Cultural Dimension

ISS is shaped by – and reflects – the Danish/Scandinavian management tradition. It contains many ingredients:

- Freedom under responsibility
- Empowerment for the individual employee and manager
- Acceptance of making mistakes
- Opportunities to make choices and take decisions
- Inclusivity and diversity
- Low power distance
- Openness
- Involvement.

ISS does not hide its national origin, but it does not brand itself on its Scandinavian origin, and management is situationally determined, so it is practiced in different ways in different parts of the world. This harmonizes with the fact that labor legislation is also very different in the various countries. Employee turnover is very different in the Scandinavian countries: high in Denmark and much lower in Sweden and Norway.

Anecdote: In connection with a roadshow to the Nordic countries, an ISS employee was to present the same concept to key account managers. The reactions were very different in the individual countries:

- In Denmark, there was a lot of challenge and loud discussions, and one was not conflict-shy in the feedback, but ended up saying: "OK, then we'll do that"
- In Sweden, it created a prolonged process, where more and more people needed to be involved and heard
- In Norway, it was met with independence, national consciousness, pride
- In Finland, it was immediately approached very systematically by drawing up Excel sheets, etc.

Management Dilemmas

Some of the management dilemmas that characterize the company's daily life can be described as:

- Balance between, on the one hand, tight economic reins, uniformity, and system focus and, on the other hand, radiating acceptance of local initiative, autonomy, and decisiveness, as long as one stays within the chalk lines
- One wants to balance on a knife-edge (= alignment), where the desire for a unifying culture, efficiency, focus on processes and systems, planning, and standardization does not suppress the strong, personal ownership, decisiveness, autonomy, the experience of being "master in one's own house", the close accountability, and attention to detail. For the group of middle managers, such as service managers, it can be a relief that "things are systematized", that one can lean on agreements and contracts, and that one can therefore refer to such agreements, rather than having to model an explanation for employees
- There is a dilemma between "customizing" the business, i.e., finding the optimal solution for the individual client, but at the same time synchronizing this with the strategy of "standardized building blocks" and uniformity. The dilemma is especially apparent in cases where ISS employees work permanently at a client's location, which can strengthen a client-oriented mindset and identity, but where ISS still wants to give employees an ISS identity
- As a final dilemma, mention must be made of the balance between letting go (a grass-roots-like respect, where there is free rein) and simultaneously marking that the common goals weigh heaviest, even though there must be room for "kindly competition" and individually tailored solutions.

Other and Previous/Later Crises Besides COVID-19

In the 1990s, the company faced a serious financial crisis when fraud was discovered in the American part of the group, resulting in an economic loss of about 2 billion DKK. The stock price plummeted, and the company's survival was at stake.

Just before the outbreak of COVID-19, ISS experienced a very serious cyber crisis: malware. All system access was lost, and within HR this meant that time registration and payroll information for 7,000 employees vanished, leaving no data on them. Email and the Office Package

worked, everything else was down. Specifically, IT department employees ran around the organization pulling network plugs, and you could only use your mobile phone if you needed to send and receive emails.

The company responded quickly and was forced to choose very pragmatic and slightly risky short-term solutions, such as paying employees a salary equivalent to the previous month's wage – and then adjusting it later. Where previously one could rely on a PC, now one had to use a notepad and pen. Where virtual meetings were once held, now one had to use the phone or go to individual workplaces to talk to people.

The situation worsened as ISS employees who worked on-site at client locations often logged on via the clients' networks, potentially spreading the cyber-attack. Nevertheless, the clients only experienced moderate concrete problems due to the crisis, and measures were taken to protect them against it.

The rug was pulled out from under the company, but it managed to rise again, gaining very significant experiences in chaos management and rapid response. A crucial catalyst was the company's tradition of delegating responsibility, autonomy, and elbow room.

Thousands of work hours were spent restoring the systems. The organizational freeze, where everything was paralyzed, took three months, and the company was actually very fragile when COVID-19 struck shortly thereafter.

The malware crisis led to closer cooperation with the trade unions. It was a common problem that employees could not receive their pay, that many thousands of files (including HR policies) were lost, that ISS could not invoice clients, and that all communication was complicated. It was in a trusting and collaborative effort that it was agreed to try to pay out the "most accurate possible" wage to the employees – and then subsequently correct any errors. The situation was dramatic because not paying wages could be perceived from the employee side as a significant breach of the employment contract by the employer.

It took up to half a year before things were somewhat back to normal, and the restoration work was enormous. One interviewee, for example, experienced receiving 32,000 restored files, which naturally made it almost impossible to find the right needles in the haystack.

"You were out on very thin ice", as it was put.

Although on a much smaller scale, it should be noted that the more extreme weather conditions in recent years have also posted significant challenges – and encompassed crisis aspects. For instance, precipitation, snow, and cold in the fall/winter of 2023-24 made it very difficult for many employees to get to work at all. This is very critical when, for example, cleaning must be done and finished at a slaughterhouse at 6:00 AM when production starts. There were instances of middle managers, in their own cars, going around to pick up their employees at their home addresses because otherwise, they would not have been able to get to work.

When COVID-19 Arrived

In hindsight (2024), COVID-19 is experienced as almost "forgotten" yet still present. In the desire to move forward (again), many of the annoyances have been repressed. But here is the picture as one looks back on it.

It is thought-provoking that ISS in fact caught wind of something new and serious before the infection even reached Denmark. This was due to ISS's global nature. A couple of months before the breakthrough and lockdown in Denmark (namely December 2019), the international top management issued warnings and handling instructions to all countries about something as "peculiar/well-known" as how to wash hands. Some major international clients reacted in the same way, and it was perceived by ISS employees as incomprehensible and dramatizing, but it meant that ISS – at least mentally – was gearing up more and more for a tsunami (epidemic/pandemic) that might be looming. ISS didn't really hit the accelerator until the infection reached Denmark, and the Prime Minister held the famous press conference on March 11, 2020.

The different parts of ISS were affected very differently. Cafeteria operations were completely shut down, reduced, or put on standby in many places, while cleaning was not radically affected, as much cleaning is less dependent on the number of people in the premises. Moreover, the increased hygiene requirements meant that there was actually growth in the need for cleaning in some areas. Clients were also affected very differently, and their commercial relationships (contracts with ISS) are also very different. This affected ISS, especially if the clients were financially pressed or even had to turn the key.

In the socially critical areas (infrastructure such as hospitals, slaughterhouses, and transport) production continued as a rule – and was even boosted in several cases because, as mentioned, COVID-19 posed new and greater demands for cleaning. Other customer areas were severely cut back or closed, e.g., food (cafeteria operations), partly because companies sent their employees home, so there was no need for cafeterias.

The problem for ISS was that the company largely provides physical services – close to and in interaction with clients' employees. This posed challenges, whether the clients' employees continued to come to the workplace (thereby increasing the risk of infection) or were sent home, and therefore there was less need for some of the services, e.g., cafeteria operations.

There was great nervousness in the organization, especially among the employees who had to continue working as before – with the consequent risk of infection. This was particularly true in the socially critical areas such as hospitals, slaughterhouses, etc. It meant a lot that the managers themselves donned work clothes, partly symbolically, partly because COVID-19 meant new rules, methods, and materials in the work, and this required hands-on management.

Due to the seriousness of the situation – and the fact that they had just been through the hacker attack (malware) – everything possible was done to ensure that the critical departments (e.g., IT and legal) were not hit by infection. They were isolated – also physically with tape around the doors, access control, guards, etc. In other parts of the organization, plans were made so that specific employees came on specific days, and there was as much physical distance as possible between those present.

Because ISS (especially regarding the broad and deep, integrated service solutions) is so close to the clients, many employees experienced two perceptions of reality: ISS's and the client's. Although ISS tried to stick to one course (= specific requirements, rules, and practices), this could vary greatly from the practices that characterized the client's premises. As expressed by an interviewee who visited a client with a very relaxed attitude to protective equipment, physical distance, etc., where the attitude was: "Corona, we don't use that here..."! As the interviewee added: "In the unbearable clarity of hindsight, ISS should have reacted to a client who took such a cavalier approach to precautions against infection".

It was therefore a complicating and frustrating circumstance that the clients' ways of interpreting and managing COVID-19 rules varied. In some places, ISS employees, for example, had to be tested to even enter the workplace, and there could be different rules for when one should report sick (e.g., due to illness at home), etc. In several cases, ISS experienced that higher demands (regarding protective equipment and preventing infection) were placed on ISS employees by the clients than they placed on their own employees. Here, ISS had to dig in its heels and emphasize that there was no basis to assume that ISS employees posed a greater risk of spreading infection than the client's own employees.

This created a cultural imbalance in the company, as COVID-19 hit so differently and therefore could be experienced as unfair. Some employees were sent home, others had to stay, some clients had their heyday, while others gasped for breath, some places had strict rules regarding protective equipment and social contact, while others moved freely.

A particular issue was the many employees of foreign origin, who wanted to visit their homelands, or who crossed national borders (especially Germany and Sweden) to come to work. Borders were closed, so ISS, for example, had to rent an entire hotel in Southern Jylland for the employees who could not cross the border, and here tensions and conflicts arose. Some employees from Eastern Europe and Asia went home and did not return when restrictions were lifted.

In summary, it can be said that COVID-19 led to a mobilization of internal muscle power. Everyone was on board, recognizing that this was new for everyone, they listened and did as they were told, the organization and the individuals showed great adaptability and willingness, took ownership, jumped in, pulled together, and put aside "We usually do...", because the situation called for entirely new solutions.

COVID-19 thus filled much of everyday life. One could almost get the impression that one thought of or worked with nothing else. However, there was also room for humor. For some, it became an internal joke that when the phone rang, they answered: "Yes, this is corona here..."!

The company was very dependent on receiving as clear communications as possible from the government, public authorities, and labor market organizations (DI and 3F). Overall, a good framework for companies' navigation through the archipelago was created by political entities, and the communication was quick and clear. The problem, however, was that the public authorities themselves did not know the answers to the many problems and challenges. And in certain areas, greater flexibility in the guidelines and frameworks that were set out could have been wished for.

Immediate Measures

The spontaneous reaction when the Prime Minister "shut down Denmark" was similar to what was found in other companies:

- Within a couple of days, about 1,400 employees were sent home – in principle without knowing whether they would receive pay. This was such a rapid decision that there was limited opportunity to involve/hear from the trade unions before the decision was announced
- Telework: sending employees home so they worked from home (remote work)
- Wage compensation: sending employees home who were released from employment and thus could not be assigned work tasks. However, after 3-4 months, the company withdrew from the wage compensation package
- Mandatory time off for overtime and vacation, which could be done via an exception in the holiday law
- Agreements on work sharing (about 120 people in total), so everyone had their working hours reduced, received pay for the reduced working hours, and unemployment benefits for the remaining part of the working hours. This was very complicated, had to be handled individually in relation to the individual location, and required negotiation with municipalities and unemployment insurance funds
- Competence development, among other things to fill "the idle time"
- Reprioritization of what was important – and good ability to put aside tasks that were not urgent
- Transferring employees to other work tasks, functions, or job types to balance surplus capacity in one place with a lack of hands elsewhere
- Security terminations, which is a method also used in "peacetime", where employees are terminated in situations where it is not known whether contracts that are expiring will be renewed
- On the other hand, terminations were used only to a very limited extent, partly in recognition that it might be difficult to get employees to return after the crisis, and that it is very costly to recruit, select, and onboard new employees
- Virtual communication (Teams meetings) saw explosive spread
- Establishment of principles for – or just rules of thumb about – managers regularly contacting sent-home employees to check how they were doing, in part to avoid distress among employees who had difficulty handling their isolated situation
- Walk-and-talk meetings, whether the meeting place was a park in Copenhagen or a rest area in Jylland.

The HR function was activated, consolidated, Personnel Law, Payroll, Employee Relations, and Workplace Environment were brought into the center, and massive communication systems and Response Teams were established that could answer questions and give advice. This was of great importance, as it made decentral managers (and their employees) feel supported. There was clear guidance, information was provided quickly and in detail about guidelines and plans, and this created consistency and transparency throughout the organization.

When COVID-19 arrived, HR generally took on a very different role. It was overwhelmed with acute tasks on all fronts: requirements and guidelines to prevent the spread of infection,

personnel law (sending home, wage compensation, rotation, etc.), psychological interventions, advising managers, stress management, etc. There also came – the completely unexpected – challenge of keeping up morale in the organization. It took on a hint of the entertainment department (Cousin HR/BR, as it was called), and that was needed because of the grim situation they were in. However, many development tasks, including competence development, were turned down low.

The overall management and coordination of the work with COVID-19 were placed in the hands of cross-organizational task forces. These also functioned as helpdesks for (especially) the managers, so they could always get advice. Due to the unfamiliar nature of the situation, this help often had the character of: "We cannot answer this here and now, but we will investigate and get back to you". Everyone was in deep water, so to speak.

The Employee Relations department played a very unique role as a competence center and helpdesk concerning personnel law, interpretation of collective agreements, legislation and agreements, business transfers (in connection with new and expired contracts), and adaptation of terms to the current situation.

All in all, the general perception that HR sits at the table and is part of the top management was clarified. HR was involved from the start, and there came (even) greater focus on and understanding for HR, respect for the law, and the HR director became more visible and took primary responsibility for communication to the organization. This ran on two tracks: internal communication to managers and employees and external communication, which had to clarify: "What do we say to the customers"?

Middle managers (especially service managers) generally have a large personnel responsibility at ISS, and this became more important during COVID-19 because:

- The situation required close dialogue with employees about everything and nothing
- If the managers could not or did not do this, it created great frustration in the team
- Employees constantly needed – and therefore should have the opportunity – to air things out with the manager
- This was the key to creating calm, trust, and support
- Oral communication was important because ISS is a very decentralized organization (with 1,000 customer locations), and because most employees do not have a private PC, do not have access to a PC at work – and most often do not have a company-paid mobile phone. (However, the app OneISS played a significant role as a written communication medium, primarily though in relation to managers and certain employee groups. Others were not reached, among other things for language reasons).

One of the biggest challenges for ISS was the relationship with the customers. They had (and still have) first priority, but it was difficult to handle bottom-up reporting from customers and front employees, including service managers, when there was also massive input in the form of guidelines, instructions, and directives from above. It was a high priority to create dialogue with the customers about which services were critical/necessary and which could be trimmed or postponed, (because staffing was reduced, and not all tasks could be solved).

To be able to handle each customer individually and flexibly, looser reins were given to the entire organization, especially the front-line managers. All aspects of the customer relationship had to be adapted to the situation, but this happened within some – by top management

set – markers of the type: "The greater leeway goes up to here, but no further". The company was aware that it thereby opened some flanks, and that the organization and customer relationship after the COVID-19 crisis needed to be brought "back to normal".

Concrete examples were employees who experienced relatively far-reaching job changes, for example, if a chef, whose job disappeared because a cafeteria was closed, instead moved to building maintenance, i.e., masonry work. In relation to existing collective agreements, it wasn't quite within the rules, but "informed intuition", sound judgment, and initiative made it work. Employees reciprocated the demonstrated flexibility with compliance (to continue being part of the organization and be assured of a job).

Communication was extremely important – from top to bottom. Top management had a fixed morning meeting every day, underlying management layers (including country managers) also had regular (but fewer) meetings, service managers were given greater responsibility for present leadership and communication, and via the app OneISS, a communication medium was created for all employees. This was challenging in itself, as many rank-and-file employees are not familiar with – and/or do not have access to – for example, PCs, and many have limited Danish/English language skills. Even at a smaller location (workplace), there can easily be 5-10 nationalities among the employees.

Webinars and other electronic news channels were also held, supplemented with communication with social content, for example, a virtual happy hour. An example was that a package containing beverages, etc., was sent to 200 employees who then connected simultaneously and drank gin & tonics – and the next time "Dark 'N' Stormy". All this was done to – by the art of the possible – create some form of contact, togetherness, and to reduce the "feeling of isolation".

ISS has many, but in relation to its size, still not so many staff representatives. Communication would have been easier to conduct all the way to the front line if there had been more staff representatives, and it would have placed a lesser burden on the shoulders of middle managers, especially in relation to employees with poor language skills, lack of IT equipment, and inability to receive written communication. Given the circumstances, however, it must be said that it was surprisingly successful in communicating messages about salary and working conditions out to the local branches of the trade unions (and thus further to the employees who were members).

The staff functions (e.g., Employee Relations) came more into play, and corporate-wide strategic task forces were formed. A massive amount of information material, Q & A lists, translations of national guidance materials (regulations, requirements, economic compensation rules), etc., were produced. This was a huge task that also required constant updating and revision, but the task was somewhat eased by having a very developed, detailed, and professional infrastructure that the company could lean on. The requirements from authorities were clear, so the company knew what it needed to do.

The psychological consequences were significant. Work was complicated, the sent home employee could experience isolation, uncertainty, stress (possibly exacerbated by their children also being sent home from their institutions/schools), and at the workplace, extreme measures were experienced. As one said, "I got up from my chair, and suddenly I saw down the hallway four employees in space suits cleaning an office area that was cordoned off with police

tape". Communication was initially complicated because, due to the recent cyber-attack, one could not send via e-boks (i.e., the national digital mailbox system). Middle managers had to get used to managing their employees from the kitchen-dining area or walking around parks with them, as it was expressed.

That some work tasks either came to be, fell away, or were solved by others than before also had consequences for the interaction with customers. For example, there were situations where a customer was contractually obligated to pay for a specific service. However, if ISS was unable to perform the work as agreed due to COVID-19, care was taken to ensure that the customer did not end up paying for the service.

Departments pulled together, stood firm, helpfulness increased, often one did not know the answers to new problems, but there was a great willingness to dig down and find answers (e.g., by asking others in the network) and come back.

Much was done to ensure that sent-home employees did not feel forgotten. In addition to Teams meetings for all employees in a team, it was emphasized that managers regularly, for example, by phone, had contact with each employee. Such "attention calls" were important, even though employees' situations were very different, and they therefore had different needs for – and desire to receive – such calls, which could be misinterpreted as control or suspicion.

The company placed great importance on being just, treating employees well, and being "super decent". This boosted loyalty among the employees, but in the initial phases, there was great uncertainty and anger because the company could not/would not tell whether it was with or without pay that one was forced home.

ISS has a long tradition of "behaving decently", which is particularly rooted in a basic assumption that "it pays off". As it was expressed: "It's foolish to neglect the risk of discovery...!", i.e., the risk of being caught if one cuts corners. Therefore, the organization is characterized by high self-regulation: "We need to be able to stand up and explain what we did".

Aftermath: When ISS Rose After COVID-19

The first half of the COVID-19 period was "a year with the heart up in the throat and a high pulse". Basically, it was unknown how long this would last and what business would be left when coming out of the tunnel and seeing the light again. And then came the second wave...

When ISS "reopened" after COVID-19, a nearly euphoric mood was seen in some. Many were happy to be "out of prison", i.e., away from home (the residence), meet their old colleagues, and hold physical meetings, etc.

However, among some, there was also a fear that the freedom, which had been given (out of necessity?) to sent-home employees, would be taken away again. There was also concern about "in what condition" the employees would return. Could they regain efficiency, (and there was actually a dip in efficiency), was the "safety culture", which is alpha and omega in a company dealing with food, hygiene, cleaning, etc., a bit frayed, could one regain an appropriate social interaction, etc.?

In fact, it was initially difficult to regain the previous efficiency and professionalism, but then came a ketchup effect, and "suddenly" one was back on track. The problems with regaining the old fitness were seen both among employees and managers. Reactions were different because individuals were affected so differently. Some had an extreme amount of work, others had less/nothing to do, some were sent home, others not, and some felt guilty because others were pushed so hard, etc.

Others felt that it had been utterly dreadful, but they would still not have wanted to be without the learning and experience that the COVID-19 period entailed.

A massive reboarding was required – and initiated – so that employees both concretely work-wise and psychologically rediscovered the rhythm as quickly as possible.

A very thought-provoking phenomenon arose, which can be called "double-sided onboarding", because it contained two parallel challenges. New employees, who were hired during the COVID-19 period, often experienced a very minimalist start, where they might not be allowed to enter the physical workplace and/or physically meet their colleagues. Parallel to this, ISS entered into contracts with new customers, but it was hard to see what the contracts entailed, because COVID-19 prevented their initiation. Thus, on both fronts, there was a need for massive onboarding, once the crisis passed. It was not until then (i.e., up to 1½ years later) that one got a hands-on impression of what kind of employees one had hired, or contracts one had entered into. Some employees and managers had disappeared, others had come along and therefore did not know the backstory.

In hindsight, it's good that one did not know from the start that the COVID-19 period would last for two years.

The company has retained/recreated its culture: "All hands to the pumps" or "All hands on deck". The action-ready, pragmatic hands-on "fix it-culture" was there before COVID-19, but was stimulated and reinforced during COVID-19, because one was immersed in acute problems and had to find new and unknown solutions.

The good cooperation with the trade unions is overall preserved during and after the COVID-19 period, and it is actually considered a prerequisite for running the business. It has been a premise – and a fundamental dilemma – and throughout the process, the company had to balance the consideration of the economic consequences (and thereby ensure survival) and be able to look the employees in the eye to maintain trust, loyalty, and solidarity. However, the process did throw off some cases, including arbitration.

The interplay between ISS as an employer and the trade unions is – and was especially during COVID-19 – largely anchored in law (legislation, political agreements, regulatory requirements, etc.). Law has not been experienced as an exact science. There are large opportunities for interpretation and gradations of the law. For example, when has there been a case of force majeure?

Business-wise, COVID-19 generally led to enormous costs, but conversely, it also generated significant growth in, for example, increased cleaning, prevention of infection spread, and these additional tasks led to increased revenue.

The fighting spirit and entrepreneurship that were mobilized due to COVID-19 evaporated when one came out on the other side – and were replaced by a certain lethargy.

It should not be forgotten that ISS experienced important shifts at the highest management levels during the same tumultuous period, including a new global CEO, a new country CEO in Denmark, and new functional business unit directors.

Crises of this type mean that decisions are both pushed up and down in the organization. Down, because one has to let go of the reins in unfamiliar areas, but also up, because top management gets whirled into (certain) very concrete operation-oriented crises and dilemmas. The board of directors, for example, suddenly got a very hands-on impression of cleaning and had to stand up in the media for very down-to-earth problems.

What Has Happened With Organizational Resilience After (and As a Result of) COVID-19?

ISS has retained its ability to act and adapt, partly because it lies in the company's DNA, and partly because it was intensively trained and homed in the many difficult decision situations caused by COVID-19.

Handling and resisting the consequences of COVID-19 necessitated massive communication from central management about procedures, guidelines, instructions, and designs, because one stood as a link between the authorities and the operational organization, and because one could not have an overview locally of what was up or down, correct or incorrect in the extraordinary situation. The company's managers and employees got better at accepting, understanding, and implementing these communications – even out at the sharp end at the individual locations. This made it easier to create a good dialogue and effective cooperation with customers.

The starting point was paradoxically quite favorable, as the cyber-attack had taught the company to (swiftly) identify the situation, uncover possible risks, identify relevant stakeholders, bring people together, unfold the issue and its consequences and branches, decide necessary actions, and implement them quickly and decisively. When hit by COVID-19, therefore, one could "plug-and-play" some of the preparedness that had been built up due to the cyber-attack.

One has learned to cooperate (better) across professional and organizational divides, gained eye contact with other professional/personnel groups, become better at seeking advice – and become better at finding the people or source materials that provided the answers to the new and difficult questions.

The individual parts of the company have "moved closer together in the bus", solidarity and co-responsibility have increased because one has gone through so much together, but there is also a fatigue and exhaustion because one has given one's all for so long.

ISS also had a solid management structure before COVID-19, a strong cultural DNA (responsibility, ownership, decision space, etc.), a well-trained corps of middle managers (service managers), a strong basic belief that the company's strategic strength is built on human resources and investment in these – and a desire for and acceptance of great diversity, regarding all the known criteria for diversity. All these characteristics have been strengthened, because

they worked during COVID-19, so there is now (even) greater awareness of how important it is to retain and develop the organizational crown jewels.

ISS has a closer and better interaction with customers, because one has been on a shared journey, had the same (and joint) challenges, had to cooperate in finding solutions – and handled this interaction in such an ethical and value-based way that the desire for cooperation has increased. The playing field in relation to the customer became completely new, and a completely new form of cooperation, solidarity, intimacy – and the experience of being in the same boat and having to save oneself ashore was created. The company has gained a greater recognition of – and a better ability to handle – the fundamentally existential basic condition, namely that on the one hand one wants to invoice as much as possible to customers, but at the same time has experienced that the customers themselves have been financially pressed.

In the HR area, the company has learned the importance of remaining relevant and attractive as a workplace, but also realized what it requires. This brings the following issues into focus:

- The importance of retaining talents
- Management of the younger generation, i.e., matching (some of) their expectations, not at any price, but in important areas (in the eyes of the young)
- Opportunities to work from home and not necessarily report to the premises
- The experience of it being demanding, but exciting to work at ISS, even though it is hard
- Conversely: Having respect for and aligning with what is a reasonable maximum burden on an employee
- The importance of work ethic and esprit de corps.

What else has the company learned?

- The toolkit and the approach one had to handle the COVID-19 crisis had many similarities with the way one handled the malware crisis
- Many prejudices about what cannot be done have been proven wrong
- One has become less fearful à la: "Whatever doesn't kill me makes me stronger"
- Mantra: "I don't know what the answer is, but I/we will find out"
- The entrepreneurship, which has always been part of the DNA, has become clearer, more valued, and triggers new ways of acting
- Autonomy has also come more into the light and is more valued/used, but is limited by the increasing emphasis on alignment, performance orientation, and KPIs, which have found their way back into the organization, after having been forced somewhat into the background during COVID-19
- Finding the balance between on the one hand a decentralized organization and autonomy and on the other hand sharp strategic markers, guiding principles, and tight management
- Every crisis contains in itself the germ of innovation. The perspective needs to be shifted from burning platform to burning desire
- One is forced to mobilize courage if one is to get through a crisis
- We have come closer to each other
- The managers had a much greater task in terms of equipping employees, but also simultaneously had to ensure feedback loops so they heard and saw what was happening out in the field
- We show greater goodwill and have become more service-minded
- We understand complex situations better, we can see through them and find solutions

- Managers have become better at engaging employees and getting them to join the journey
- You reap what you sow. If one already – as a manager – has built trust and has a group of employees with competence and passion, one is much better equipped than if this is lacking. A (highly placed) manager said, for example: "My leadership style is transparent, (so I can also show vulnerability), authentic, value- and team-based, and that provided a solid foundation for doing the right thing. I still have my leadership group, it is intact, and no one went down with the flag (due to stress) during the process"
- A "tight-loose approach" was very important: We communicate, listen, and discuss, but hard decisions are also made, and some of these – also the most important ones – are categorically announced and are not up for discussion. It can be overwhelming, but also provides clear lines and creates peace at the back: "OK, then we know what we have to adhere to. The race is run, and then we roll up our sleeves"
- Quite simply: the most important thing is what one does, not what one says
- Even though (or precisely because) the situation was chaotic, it was crucial to try to optimize psychological safety
- Employees were affected very differently, among other things due to their different private life situations (e.g., marital status (singles, families with children, etc.), ethnic background, and nationality). The interaction between the central HR functions and the operational organization became closer and better as a result of COVID-19. The dialogue was intensified, HR came to occupy more space at manager and employee meetings, and the individual manager had better opportunities (and was better equipped) to exercise personnel management – and seek advice in HR if this was required. Ultimately, this contributed to reducing the uncertainty and insecurity that was a latent challenge throughout the organization – and throughout the process. What would one have done differently if one had the insight one has today?
- Fire fewer people, because thereby one could have avoided (some) of the desperate lack of labor that exists in selected areas – and in a labor market where the individual person has several/many options outside of ISS
- (Even) closer communication with the trade unions, where one is somewhat a victim of the perception that one thinks "one has communicated enough", rather than starting from the recipient's experience of what it takes, and whether the communication is received and understood
- There should have been a greater degree of writing in the communication with the trade unions, so it stands clearer what one means, has agreed, and communicated. (Well knowing that in some situations it can be lucky not to have written too much down!).

What are the challenges?

ISS is a decentralized organization – and became even more so during (and as a result of) COVID-19. The greater autonomy was well-founded (read: necessary) during COVID-19, but it blurred efficiency. There has been a concrete drop in efficiency, and one is now trying to regain it by greater system focus, sharpened KPIs, by casting a critical eye on the hours spent on individual work tasks, generally cutting to the bone, and slaughtering sacred cows.

We are strong but need to be stronger.

We are not good enough at saying that we are a service company, and that we deliver the optimal service experience.

On the HR front, there are, among other things, the following three concrete challenges, i.e., signature moves, which are handshakes that one will give each other throughout the corporation, and which must be followed at all destinations:

- Up-skilling, so that one also masters future work tasks
- Efforts regarding refugees. (For example, ISS has most recently employed 100 Ukrainian refugees).

Other challenges, however, overlap with the preceding:

- Recruiting in a red-hot labor market. Worldwide, approximately 125,000 employees are hired annually. In Denmark, it is about 1,500
- New and better sourcing (access to new labor markets)
- Onboarding
- Development of employees
- Acceptance of new employee categories (diversity).

ISS has such a complex and broad-spectrum product and customer portfolio that it cannot achieve the same systematics, standardization, simplification, and routinization as a McDonald's restaurant. This at the same time provides opportunities for and demands that there is great decentral resilience, competence, and readiness to act.

Within the HR organization, some of the challenges are:

- Establishment/strengthening of shared service centers
- Automation and robotization
- Chatbot technology
- We must standardize before we can automate.

Note:

This case report is an outcome of the following research project:

Investigating the distinctive features and resilience of human resource management in the Nordic countries: A longitudinal and cross-national study

Authors: Frans Bévort and Henrik Holt Larsen, CBS, Copenhagen Business School

Sponsor: Sveriges Riksbank

Grant administrator: Göteborgs Universitet

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Appendix

Values: [ISS Values and History](#)

UNITY

We trust each other and believe we can create equality, inclusion, and cohesion for everyone—a culture where everyone can be themselves. We trust. It's about building diverse talents and teams, creating space for collaboration, and learning about and from others. When we collaborate, we deliver a better experience to our customers and their communities. Only together can we live up to our purpose.

HONESTY

We do not compromise on our honesty. We respect our customers, our colleagues, and our company. We show respect. We have a proud tradition of fairness, equality, and inclusion. Every day we strive to create a culture based on open communication and collaboration, where differences and individual contributions are respected and recognized.

RESPONSIBILITY

Indifference is immoral. We engage in our work and those we work for. We show care. The health and well-being of our employees and customers are our top priority. We want our employees to be happy, feel valued, and thrive. Therefore, we make great efforts to create a safe and comfortable work environment and improve the local communities we work in.

ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Action means more than words. All our employees have the right to act, and we expect them to do so. We act. At ISS, we lead by example. We empower our employees to act and contribute to innovation—whether they suggest improvements and new methods of work or draw attention to behavior that undermines our vision and values. Our employees know they have our support to do the right thing.

QUALITY

We are passionate about delivering high quality. We keep what we promise. We deliver the goods. Our employees are part of a large global team working towards the same purpose—to deliver exceptional service experiences. We can offer well-trained, resourceful, and motivated employees who strive to provide high-quality services every day.